

Research Article

PARADIGMATIC AND SYNTAGMATIC RELATIONS IN PHRASES MEANING "SPEECH" IN UZBEK AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

Linguistics

Keywords: phraseme, phrase-semema, phrases meaning "speech", paradigmatic relationship, syntagmatic relationship, base member.

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Abstract

The paper analyzes the paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations in the phrase "speech" in Uzbek and Karakalpak languages. Phrases have a certain paradigm for connecting with other parts of speech and are based on syntactic functions.

According to Prof. B.Yuldashev, on the morphological structure and paradigm of phrases V.P.Zhukov, A.M.Chepasova, L.V.Semenkova, A.V.Zhukov, V.N.Grishanova, on the syntactic function of phrases in speech The researches of such scientists as S.G. Gavrin, L.A.Kim, O.V.Shavkunova, V.M.Burmakov have been published [1, C. 5].

The base member is represented by a noun lexeme, part of the phrases whose syntactic structure is equal to the compound belongs to the category of adjectives. Such phrases differ from noun phrases in content (with the semantic "qualitative sign of the subject") and grammatical form. The adjective does not participate in the phrasal verb, the numerator and the denominator, it comes in the speech as an adjective (accordingly, the syntactic semantic "adjective" is added) [2, C 192].

Speech phrases are mainly composed of adjectives with the base member adjective and non-adjective adjectives with the relative noun.

The main phrase of the *til(i) kesik* is connected to the next part of the base member without any grammatical means. For example: *Yo'lchi... bir zumda odamlarga qarab chiqdi. Ba'zilarining ko'zida zulmga nafrat, ba'zilarida yolg'iz, qo'rquv ko'rdi: Hammaning tili kesik, faqat shipga osilgan bedanalar urinadi* (Oybek).

The phrase of the *nafasi sovuq* takes on the morphemes that the noun accepts when grazing, and enters into a grammatical relationship. For example: *Bu nafasi sovuqni qishloqdan haydash kerak! (S.Anorboev). Otga bog'lanib kelganda esa grammatik ko'rsatkich olmaydi. Misol: Vilyam dedingizmi? Muncha ham nafasi sovuq odam ekan* (S.Nazar).

The Karakalpak language's *awizi jeñil, sozi otkir* phrases accept morphemes and enter into grammatical relationships similar to Uzbek phrases. For example: *Oniñ awizi jeñil. Uyat-ábireysiz, keldi-ketpeli gápler shıg'adı oniñ awızınan* (M.Nızanov).

Nayatiy **ótkir dim sózi** zaʻgʻardiʻ,
 “Qaymiqpasaʻ tilip keter qilishtay (H.Ayymbetov).

It turns out that quality phrases are not specific to use in grammatical forms. We have seen that quality phrases do not form grammatically even in phrases whose construction is similar to the verb in the above view.

In phrasal verbs, where the base member is represented by the functional forms of the verb, the base member takes the morpheme *-da* in the adjective form *-gan*, and expresses the meaning of the tense. As a phrase **ogʻiz juftlaganida**. For example: *Bizga koʻzi tushib, bir narsa demoqchi boʻlib ogʻiz juftlaganida, Golovin uning soʻzini boʻldi. (M.Muhamedov)*. When auxiliary verbs are added to a phrase, suffixes are added to the last component: *Bir narsa aytmoqchi boʻlib ogʻzimni juftlab turgan edim, telefon jiringlab qoldi. (Oydin)*.

The first component of the phrase **lab(i) lab(i)ga tegmay** received the adjective, the second component received the adjective and the prepositional suffix, the third component received the infinitive form of the verb and the adverbial participle. Has been stating the status of the execution of the action. For example: *Hojimat labi labiga tegmay javrab ketdi (S.Ahmad)*. *Undan narida bir qalandar labi labiga tegmay gʻazal oʻqiydi (Sh.Toshmatov)*.

The structure of the Karakalpak phrases **erini erinine tiymey (labi labiga tegmay), jagʻi jagʻina juqpay (jagʻi jagʻiga tegmay), awizi-awizina juqpay (ogʻzi-ogʻziga tegmay)**, the morphological features of the components are similar to the Uzbek phrase **labi labiga tegmay**. For example: *Bala Shumbaydan qashan shuqqanin, keshirim xat algʻanin, qandasin kórip ketiwge kelgenin, qudasiniʻ “búginen qalsa kóre almay qalasaʻ”, degenin awizi-awizina juqpay, sawdirap aytıp shuqtı (Sh.Seytov)*.

The first and second components of the phrase **"lom-mim" demay** are the names of the letters in the Arabic orthography, which are used in the figurative sense of "absolutely not speaking". The third component took the infinitive form of the verb and the adverbial participle. Indicates the status of the execution of the action. Sometimes the **-u** partical can also be used to link the first and second components. For example: *Hamma uning aytganini “lom-mim” demay bajarayotganini Rahim koʻrib turgan edi (H.Nazir)*. *Qolgan fuqarolarning osoyishtalik bilan kori-xayr ishida “lom”-u “mim” demay ishlamoqlari lozim ekanini soʻyladi (Gʻ.Gʻulom)*.

The first component of the **ikki ogʻiz** phrases is number, the second component is noun, and represents the meaning of quantity. It is connected to the next part without any morphological indications. Allophrases in the form of **bir-ikki ogʻiz, ikki-uch ogʻiz** are also used in speech. For example: *Siz bilan bir-ikki ogʻiz suhbatlashgani kelgan edim (N.Maqsudiy)*. *Joʻra... mehmonlar tomonga bemalol yurib bordi, hatto baʻzilari bilan ikki-uch ogʻiz soʻzlashib, koʻchaga chiqib ketdi (Oybek)*.

The first noun component of Karakalpak phrases *tilin jutup qoyg'anday (tilini yutib qo'yganday)*, *awızın buwg'an ógizdey (og'zini bog'lagan ho'kizday)* is the suffix (-n), the second verb component is the first adjective (-ip), the second adjective is the adjective (-g'an), the third component is the adjective adjective (-g'an) in the first phrase. then the imitation suffix (-day) is connected to the next piece by obtaining the third noun component imitation suffix (-day) in the second phrase. For example: *Qalbay tilin jutup qoyg'anday ses semirsiz qaldı (A.Baymuratova)*. *Qalbay ele tilin jutup alg'anday únsiz kiyatır (A.Baymuratova)*. *Ushpag'a qanati bolmay asıg'ıp otırg'an jigit, endi álle nemirge shekem awızın buwg'an baspaqtay úndemey otırdı (Ó.Xojaniyazov)*. – *Bizniń bir jaman jiyenniń úyi bar. Sog'an barayıq, – dedi kúni menen awızın buwg'an ógizdey tum-tırıs kiyatırg'an Sayımbet (Ó.Xojaniyazov)*.

Prof. Sh. Rahmatullaev firstly divides phrases into connected and unconnected phrases in his study "Connection of verb phrases in the Uzbek language". Connected phrases are: a) single-connected; b) two-linked; c) classifies as three-connected phrases. Single-connected phrases are: a) phrases associated with the owner; b) phrases associated with the focus; c) analyzes into three as phrases associated with the filler. Two conjunctive verb phrases are: a) possessive and accusative conjunctive phrases; possessive and case-related phrases. The three-linked verb analyzes the phrases separately [4, p. 125].

Karakalpak linguist J.Tanirbergenov studied the structural types and paradigmatic features of verb phraseology in the Karakalpak language in the third chapter of his dissertation "Linguistic analysis of verb phraseology in the Karakalpak language." The first section of the chapter, entitled "Structural types of verb phraseology", studies the structure and construction models of verb phraseology in the Karakalpak language. The second section, entitled The Paradigm of Verb Phraseologisms, analyzes the paradigmatic forms of verb phraseology. In the third section, entitled "Divisible and non-divisible forms of verb phraseology": 1. Used in both divisible and indivisible forms: 2. Used in divisible form: 3. Verbs used in indivisible form are classified into phrases [5, P.19-23].

When a phrase is introduced into speech, it enters into a grammatical relationship with other language units and serves to express the idea effectively, figuratively. Although structurally equal to a compound, a sentence, or different types of a sentence, in a sentence it mainly serves as a part of speech and is associated with words in different functions. Such a connection is called a syntactic circle. The fact that a phrase has a syntactic encirclement depends on its category, its internal syntactic structure, the control of the verb word-component in verb phrases, and whether this control is realized or not within the phrase, the possessive affix involved in the noun component.

The ability of phrases to connect is largely determined by which category they belong to. In the examples we have collected, there is no phrase "speech" in both languages. It was found that most of them belonged to the category of verbs, and a small part to the category of adjectives and adverbs.

I. The connection of quality phrases depends on the syntactic structure and function of the sentence.

1. Phrases of equal construction:

a) the noun is connected to the lexeme and comes in the role of adjective in the sentence: *shirin so‘z yigit, og‘zi mahkam brigadir, otash zabon shoir* and other. For example: “*Brigadir deganingiz... og‘zi mahkammi?*” – “*Bu tomondan shubham yo‘q, mana to‘rt yildan buyon changini chiqarmaydi*”. (R.Fayziy).

U ming‘irlab, ma‘ruzachi otash zabon ko‘p qadrli shoirlarga til tegizganini aytib, “Adabyotimizning gullari bo‘lgan u muhtaram shoirlarning obro‘cini tushirish g‘oyat uyat, fojii”, – dedi (Oybek).

In Karakalpak language: *tili ashshu hayal, awizi ashq adam, tili mayli adam*. For example: *Qalay oylamasin? Tili mayli adam. Amanliqqa takir-tykirlilik etpeydi* (T.Qayipbergenov). It has been found that rotation from sentence-like construction to compound construction and vice versa is very rare in phrases meaning "speech". The phrase *awizi ashq (og‘zi ochiq)* in the Karakalpak language has the same structure as a sentence, and in the "Phraseological dictionary of the Karakalpak language" it means "gossiper, unable to keep a secret" [6, C.17]. The phrase *awizi ashq (og‘zi ochiq)* has also been shown to mean "gossiper who cannot keep a secret" [6, C.22]. For example: *Sariatawdin‘in usti menen Shag‘al jag‘isina tawir-aq qalg‘anda bir sharwani‘in uyine qos basti. uy iyesi anqildag‘an ashq awiz adam eken, bir serkeni kehespesten jayratti da tasladi* (Sh.Seyitov).

The first of the phrases is of equal construction to the sentence, the second to the compound. For example: “*Bar, joldas Saparov. Men siz aytqanday anqawda, awizina kók shubin kirip shug‘atug‘in awizi ashq ta emespen, bildiniz be!*” (Sh.Seyitov). – *Awizi ashq bolmasan, shabarman degen za‘ng‘ardan ispolkomni‘in parmanin soramaymisan, tildey qag‘az almaymisan! – dep kuyindi Saparov* (Sh.Seyitov).

b) binds to the subject and comes as a predicate in the sentence, such as *tili uzun, tili o‘tkir*. For example: *Shu tobda uning tili uzun edi, chunki u hammadan oldin o‘z uyidan bir zambilg‘altak novda keltirgan edi* (H.Nazir). *Gapingni bilib gapir, hushyorroq muomala qil. Ko‘ngli nozik, tili o‘tkir – bir so‘z bilan umidingni shart kesib qo‘yishi mumkin*(I.Rahim).

In Karakalpak language: As a *tili bay (juyrik), tili muki, sozi otkir*. For example: *Qaraqalpaq xalqi – sozge sheber, tili bay, har bir aytqan sozin naqil-maqal, frazeologizm menen tastiyqlap soyleytug‘in xaliq* (A.Pirniyazova). *Soni alamis, son uyde kimni‘in sozi otkir ekenin bilip qoyadi* (B. Ziywarova).

2. Compounds of equal sentence-form:

1) the noun is attached to the lexeme and comes as an adjective; in which the preposition is omitted and the syntactic semantic "adjective" is added; often has a comparator involved in the composition of the unit; usually a III person relative, sometimes another person-number relative. For example: **Tili achchiq**. *Balki bu yosh yigitning (Sherbekning) tili achchiqdir... Balki u ba'zi birovlar qilgani kabi hayotimizdagi nuqsonlarni ko'ra-bila turib ko'z yumib o'ta olmas (S.Anorboev). Elmurodga rota komandiri yoqmad, qalampir, tili achchiq, har gapni pisanda qilganday, burab gapiradi (Shuhrat).*

In Karakalpak language: As a **tili záhár (uwayday), awızı buzıq**.

*Men tentekpen **tilim ashshi záhárdey,**
Teñep júrmeh' a jaqqan báhárdey (Arıwxan).*

2) Comes as a speech function; the possessive member of the phrasal verb is composed of a relative and one of the three person-number relative is selected selectively; hence, in such phrases there is a possibility of connection with the focusing piece; base member:

a) The verb in the present-future tense form is represented by a lexeme: **bir sózi eki shıqtı (kimning), aytıwg'a tili (awızı) barmadı (kimning)**. For example: *Sen uslap tutqan buyımlardı mañlayına tiygizip, súyip jıladı. Onı qoydıra almadım. Qoy dep aytıwg'a tilim barmadı (M.Nızanov). Ondag'ı eki jas pa? Onda bizler-ám eki jıldan keyin... – Arjag'in aytıwg'a awızım barmadı (M.Nızanov).*

b) The adjective is represented by a lexeme: *Atrıń tórt buwınnan, aytıwg'a tilge awır (I.Yusupov)*

Hence, a phrasal verb (equivalent to any syntactic unit in general) is used in speech as a sentence (sentence) in accordance with its syntactic structure, as well as as part of a compound (e.g., adjective) with its place.

II. Regardless of the syntactic structure and grammatical form of adverb phrases, the verb lexeme is connected to the cut lexeme and serves as a declension: *og'ziga kelganini bo'g'zidan qaytarmay haqorat qildi, tilingizni bir qarich qilib gapir-, ikki og'izgina suhbatlash-, in Karakalpak: awızın ashaman degenshe bolıw, awızına qum quyılğ'anday sóylemedi, tilin jutıp qoyğ'anday úndemeydi.*

III. The verb phrase consists of at least two lexemes. In verb phrases, the base member is represented by a verb lexeme, while the infinitive is represented mainly by a noun lexeme, sometimes by another category lexeme. The possibility of connecting a verb phrase is determined primarily by the verb lexeme it contains.

It has been shown in the literature that the connection of verb phrases is much more complex and diverse than that of noun, adjective, and form phrases. In the examples we have

collected, it has been found that verb phrases meaning “speech” also have one-syllable, two-syllable, and three-syllable phrases. Single related phrases:

The prepositional is formed: *og‘z(i)dan bol tomadi (kimning), gap(i)dan latta hidi keladi (kimning)*. The fragment possessed in this phrase is represented by a focusing compound. In the Karakalpak language: *awızınan pal tamadı, sózinen pal tamadı*.

*Kórip turg‘an joqpan ba ya túsimde,
Sóylegenin pal tamızıp sózinen* (A.Qayıpov).

As a third member, the participle in the future tense is present: *chakagi chakagiga tegmaydi* (nimaning). In Karakalpak: *awızı awızına juqpadı (tiymedi), erini erinine tiymeydi, jag‘ı jag‘ına juqpadı*.

The following forms of two-connected verb phrases meaning "speech" were encountered:

1) The means attached to the phrasema is formed in the complementary accusative case.

a) Phraseme contains an indirect filler: *gap bermoq* (kim kimga), *dakki bermoq* (kim kimga), *baytu g‘azallar aytmoq* (kim kimning sha‘niga).

In the last phrase, the medium is represented by a filler compound. Apparently, the future of the unmediated filler in this type of phrasal verb is usually unmarked. Only one phrase is characterized by unmediated filler: *gapni to‘kib solmoq* (kim kimga).

b) The phrasal verb consists of the infinitive and the infinitive formed in the accusative case: *gapini og‘zidan oldirmoq* (kim kimga).

2) The means connected to the phrasema is formed in the filler accusative case:

a) The phrasal verb contains indirect filler: *gapini og‘zidan oldirmoq* (kim kimga).

b) In addition to the indirect filler, the phrasal verb is also present: *gapini og‘zidan yulmoq* (kim kimdan). This phrasal verb is represented by an adjective compound without a medium.

3) The auxiliary with the filler, which is attached to the phrasal verb, forms an auxiliary, the phrasal verb contains the mediator filler: *og‘zining tanobini tortmoq* (kim kimning), *til-jag‘ini bog‘lamoq* (kim kimning). In the last two phrases came a predicative syntagm in the function of unmediated filler.

“Among the phrases that have a meaning of speech, there is a phrasal verb that has three conjunctions and is a type of phrasal verb with a complement. The association of such a phrase with the subject is usually referred to as the person (*nima (o‘zining) kimni*).

The association of this type of phrasal verbs with the accusative is also referred to as human. In only one phrase did the connection with the focuser turn out to be about something: pulling the *uchini chiqarmoq* (*kim nimaning, kimga*). Apparently, this phrase contains a mediator complement in the directional contraction; the verb member is represented by a generalized verb.

References

1. Yo‘ldoshev. B. O‘zbek frazeologiyasi va frazeografiyasi masalalari. – Toshkent: Muharrir, 2013. – S. 5.
2. Rahmatullaev Sh. Hozirgi adabiy o‘zbek tili. Ikkinchi kitob. – Toshkent: Mumtoz so‘z, 2010. – S. 192.
3. Rahmatullaev Sh. O‘zbek tilining frazeologik lug‘ati. –Toshkent: Qomuslar Bosh tahririyati, 1992. – 380 s.
4. Rahmatullaev Sh. O‘zbek tilida fe'l frazemalarning bog‘lashuvi. – Toshkent: Universitet, 1992. – S. 125.
5. Tanirbergenov J. Qoraqalpoq tilida fe'l frazeologizmlarning lingvistik tahlili. Filol. fan. bo‘y. fals. dokt. (PhD) diss. avtoref. – Nukus, 2020. – S. 19-23.
6. Paxratdinov Q., Bekniyazov Q. Qaraqalpaq tiliniń frazeologizmler sózligi. – Nókis: Qaraqalpaqstan, 2018. 160 s.